

GEOGRAFIYA FANIDAN AMALIY MASHG'ULOTLAR: TALABALAR BILIMINI OSHIRISHNING SAMARALI USULLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tabaqalashtirilgan geografiya darslarini o'tkazishning ahamiyati va samaradorligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Tabaqalashtirilgan usullarning talabalarning akademik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'siri va fanga qiziqish ortishi o'rganiladi. Geoaxborot tizimlari (GIS), interaktiv xaritalar va multimediya yordamida bilimlarni o'zlashtirishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar taklif etiladi, raqamli usullar bilan bilim sifatini oshirish yo'llari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение и эффективность проведения дифференцированных занятий по географии. Изучается влияние дифференцированных методов на успеваемость учащихся и повышение интереса к предмету. Предложены современные подходы к усвоению знаний с использованием средств геоинформационных систем (ГИС), интерактивных карт и мультимедиа, рассмотрены пути повышения качества знаний цифровыми методами.

Annotation. This article discusses the importance and effectiveness of conducting practice classes in geography. The influence of practical methods on improving students' academic performance and interest in the subject is studied. Modern approaches to knowledge acquisition through the use of Geoinformation systems (GIS), interactive maps and multimedia tools are proposed, and ways to improve the quality of knowledge by digital methods are considered.

Kalit so'zlar: geografiya, amaliy mashg'ulotlar, geografik axborot tizimlari, interfaol texnologiyalar, ta'lim sifatini oshirish

Ключевые слова: география, практические занятия, географические информационные системы, интерактивные технологии, повышение качества образования

Keywords: geography, practice classes, Geoinformation systems, interactive technologies, improving the quality of Education

The subject of geography is one of the most important disciplines that contributes to the development of students' abilities for spatial thinking, understanding of natural and social phenomena. However, for the full assimilation of theoretical knowledge, the formation of practical skills is especially important. Practice classes enrich the educational process, allowing students to apply scientific methods, analyze data and implement methods of studying the environment in practice. In the modern education system, the role of practice classes is growing, as they increase the motivation of students to study, arouse interest in the subject, and also form the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in life.

The purpose of this study is to identify the impact of practical classes in geography on improving students' knowledge, to identify effective methods and techniques for improving their learning outcomes. As part of the study, the following tasks are set:

1. To determine the essence and significance of practical work in Geography lessons;
2. Analysis of various methods of organizing practical classes in the educational process;

3. Assessment of the impact of practical classes on the level of knowledge and interest of students in the subject;

4. Provide effective methods and technologies that can be used in pedagogical practice.

This study provides for the formation of a comprehensive understanding of the influence and importance of practice classes in teaching geography, which will contribute to improving educational practice and improving the level of knowledge of students.

Practical classes are one of the most important tools for students to learn geography, as they introduce interactivity into the learning process and increase the activity of students. The combination of theoretical knowledge with practical skills helps students to comprehensively master the material, memorize new information, develop the skills of conducting real research and analyzing. Practical classes also increase interest in the subject and encourage students to work independently, which contributes to a deeper and more conscious assimilation of knowledge. [1]

The advantages of practical classes include the formation of students' research skills, understanding of natural and social phenomena through experience, as well as scientific research and research.

From a psychological and pedagogical point of view, practice classes are an effective method of teaching, as they stimulate the active cognitive activities of students and allow them to use various methodologies in the educational process. Scientists such as Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky and John Dewey considered learning methods based on experiential learning to be effective for Human Cognitive and social development. Piaget emphasized the need to actively build knowledge, while Vygotsky emphasized the importance of differentiated tasks according to the level of development of students. [2]

Practice classes contribute to the independent development of the student, the disclosure of individual abilities, the expression of their own thoughts and active participation in the subject. From the psychological point of view, practical classes increase enthusiasm and interest in mastering new knowledge, because students draw results with their own hands using theoretical knowledge. This allows them to remember the knowledge gained for a long time, to make independent decisions. [3]

Table 1 - effective methods of organizing practice classes

M ethod	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
P roject work	Planning and execution of the project on the topic.	Develops creative and teamwork skills.	It takes a lot of time and preparation.
R esearch work	The study of the phenomenon through scientific methods.	Develops skills in analyzing and working with data.	Additional tools are needed, there are difficult topics.
Fi eld work	Study of phenomena in the natural environment.	Helps to understand the environment.	Weather-dependent, security is necessary.

In teractive technolo gies	Learning through virtual cards and Multimedia.	Makes the educational process interesting, develops thinking skills.	Can be expensive, requires special training.
D igital technolo gies	The use of GIS and data analysis tools.	Develops analytical skills.	Equipment and training are required.

In the modern educational process, digital and interactive technologies are widely used to increase students' interest in the subject of geography and high-quality assimilation of knowledge. These technologies make it possible to visually represent geographical phenomena and processes, effectively analyze information, and develop spatial thinking. An important role as the main tools is played by Geoinformation systems (GIS), interactive maps and multimedia resources. [4]

GIS tools allow you to summarize, analyze and present geographic information visually. With this technology, students learn to explore data in real time and evaluate natural and social phenomena locally and globally. For example, with the help of GIS, they can study the environmental situation of a particular territory, combine various data and track regional changes. This contributes to the formation of analytical skills and the practical knowledge of students in life.

Application of GIS tools:

1. **Systematization of geographic information:** students work with spatial data by adding data in layers, understanding and processing maps.

2. **Visualization and analysis:** graphical representation of geographic data, visualization of the relationships between data.

3. **Development of scientific research skills:** with the help of the tool, comprehensive analyzes are made on specific topics, which develops students' research skills.

Through interactive maps, virtual trips and multimedia tools, it is possible to present geographical data and phenomena to students in a clear and interesting way. These tools greatly contribute to the development of cartographic and spatial thinking, as they allow students to assimilate information not only theoretically, but also visually. *Інтерактивті карталар мен мультимедиа құралдарын қолдану:*

1. **Development of cartographic thinking:** through interactive maps, students see the location of different geographical objects, their relationship with each other.

2. **Spatial thinking:** visualizing geographical phenomena through multimedia tools improves spatial understanding, which helps students better understand the processes of the Earth's surface.

3. **Activation of the educational process:** virtual trips and video materials make classes more attractive and contribute to the effective acquisition of knowledge.

With the help of digital and interactive technologies, the teaching of geography becomes deeper and more interesting. These technologies are aimed at developing students' spatial thinking skills, increasing interest in the subject and applying the knowledge gained in real life.

Practical classes have a positive effect on academic performance, as they allow you to connect theoretical knowledge with practice. Students, applying the material in practice, learn it better and remember it for a long time. Research shows that in classes where practical methods are

used, the quality of students' knowledge increases, because they not only listen to the educational material, but also perform it in practice. Thanks to practice classes, the results of students, assessment indicators and the level of knowledge are significantly improved.

Practice classes increase students' interest in the subject and strengthen their motivation to learn. Practical methods encourage students to actively participate in the learning process, demonstrating the importance of understanding the subject and applying it in life. As students' interest in the subject increases, their motivation and motivation for the lesson increases, which, in turn, contributes to the improvement of educational results. Are practice classes an interest

Practical classes have a great impact on the quality of education and motivation of students. They not only facilitate students' understanding of the subject, but also develop their creative and research skills. Practice classes play an important role in the formation of students' learning outcomes, interest and a positive attitude to the subject. The combination of theory and practice ensures the consolidation of knowledge and its application in life, which increases the overall quality of knowledge of students.

To further increase the effectiveness of practice classes, the following recommendations should be taken into account:

1. **Improvement of tools:** wide use of Geoinformation systems, virtual maps and other digital technologies in the learning process.

2. **Application of different teaching methods:** combining different methods, for example, combining research work with the project method, diversifying the content of the lesson and allowing students to fully develop their cognitive abilities.

3. **Professional development of teachers:** organization of special courses for the development of teachers' skills in working with digital and interactive technologies.

4. **Introduction of individual teaching methods:** personalization of practice classes and organization of tasks at different levels, taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

These recommendations will make it possible to organize practical classes more efficiently and further improve the quality of students' education.

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